

A reduced chemical mechanism for the simulation of electrified methane/air flames

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Abstract

A reduced mechanism for the prediction of methane/air flames impinged by external electric fields is presented in this work. This mechanism is composed of 26 species and 134 reactions and predicts the electric current produced by a burner stabilized flame with similar accuracy as the state-of-the-art mechanisms while using a fraction of their species and reactions. Thus, the proposed mechanism guarantees a significant reduction of the computational cost without penalties in the accuracy of electrified methane/air flames calculations.

1. Introduction

The numerical simulation of the interaction between external electric fields and hydrocarbon flames is often inhibited by several computational challenges. The interaction of phenomena occurring over a broad spectrum of time scales, the need for complex transport models, and the need for detailed chemical mechanisms are just a few examples of the difficulties faced in the recently published numerical investigations [1–7]. Even though significant advances in the context of the numerical methods for the simulation of flames impinged by external electric fields have been made in the last years [8], producing accurate reduced chemical mechanisms that incorporate chemi-ionization phenomena appears fundamental to perform the simulation of electrified flames in complex geometries.

The main efforts regarding the definition of accurate chemical mechanisms that include chemi-ionization mainly deal with methane/air combustion. The works by Speelman *et al.* [9, 10] are the first attempts to perform a one-to-one comparison of numerical and experimental results for the ion current produced by a flame. The mechanism proposed in those works is based on the neutral chemistry of the Grimech 3.0 [11], which is supplemented with the three-step chemi-ionization mechanism proposed by Belhi *et al.* [1]. The main shortcoming of this kinetic model is the high concentration of the radical CH in the reacting layer of the flame, which leads to an overprediction of the ion current. This inaccuracy was palliated by the same authors performing an empirical optimization of rate coefficients and charged species transport properties. Belhi *et al.* [12] presented a detailed mechanism that could be considered the benchmark for the evaluation of the accuracy of ion current flames impinged by electric fields. This

mechanism was assembled using a modified version of the Aramco v. 1.4 mechanism, which consists of 311 species and 1831 reactions, for the neutral chemistry and an updated version of the ion-chemistry proposed by Prager *et al.* [13], which contains 68 reactions and includes the free electrons, four positive ions, and six negative ions. This chemical scheme, coupled with state-of-the-art models for the prediction of ion transport properties [14, 15], leads to accurate predictions of the experimental data in Ref. [10].

The above-mentioned chemical mechanism considers hundreds of species and thousands of reactions. Such a detailed description of the mixture is untenable for the two-dimensional and three-dimensional numerical simulation of electrified flames. For this reason, this work proposes a reaction mechanism for methane/air flames that preserves accurate predictions of the ionization rates while considering a reduced number of species and reactions.

The accuracy of the proposed mechanism is assessed by comparing its results with the experimental profiles of ion-current density extracted in the burner-stabilized methane/air flames studied by Speelman *et al.* [10]. This experimental setup consists of a heat flux burner that produces a one-dimensional flat flame. The burner is fed with a mixture of methane and air at ambient pressure which flows at the laminar flame velocity developed by the same mixture at 298 K. The burner is kept at 350 K to stabilize the flat premixed flame and it is electrically grounded. A mesh electrode is positioned 1 cm downstream of the burner and is attached to a voltage generator to impose a one-dimensional electric field. The setup has been studied for three different equivalence ratios of the feeding mixture equal to $\phi = 0.8, 1.0,$ and 1.2 .

2. Methodology

The proposed kinetic mechanism is obtained from the analytic reduction of the detailed kinetic mechanisms for

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Figure 1: Profiles of ion current density produced by the flame at $\phi = 0.8$ (a), 1.0 (b), and 1.2 (c) versus the applied difference of potential. The plot shows the results of the experiments (blue symbols), of the numerical (red dashed line) and optimized numerical (red line with symbols) calculations by Speelman *et al.* [10]. The red solid line shows the numerical results presented by Belhi *et al.* [12]. The black diamonds, the black circles, and the black solid line correspond to the prediction of the “detailed”, “modified”, reduced mechanisms, respectively. The ion current density is multiplied by a factors 10 in panel (a) and 20 in panels (b, c) for the cases at negative polarity.

neutral chemistry of C1-C4 hydrocarbons proposed in Ref. [16–Ref. [12] to the Aramco v. 1.4 mechanism, the preexponential factor of the reactions (R1) and (R2) have been changed from $3 \times 10^{13} \text{ cm}^3/(\text{mol s})$ to $2.83 \times 10^{14} \text{ cm}^3/(\text{mol s})$ and from $1.774 \times 10^{16} \text{ cm}^3/(\text{mol s})$ to $1.713 \times 10^{13} \text{ cm}^3/(\text{mol s})$, respectively. The activation energy of the reaction (R1) has been set 735 cal/mol, whereas the temperature exponent and the activation energy of the reaction (R2) have been set to 0 and -755 cal/mol , respectively. The results obtained using the standard reaction mechanism will be from now on denoted with the “detailed” label meanwhile those obtained with the modified chemistry will be referred to as “modified”.

The described mechanism has been reduced using the direct relation graph with error propagation method implemented in the software ARCANE [21, 22]. The reduction procedure has been applied considering the numerical solutions of the flames at the three different equivalence ratios of the experiment and with electric potential difference imposed at the electrodes equal to $\Delta\Phi = -250 \text{ V}, -150 \text{ V}, -50 \text{ V}, 50 \text{ V}, 90 \text{ V}, 130 \text{ V}, 170 \text{ V}, 210 \text{ V},$ and 250 V . These numerical solutions have been computed using the open-source solver CANTERA [23], whereby minor modifications have been included to set the boundary conditions of the problem and to output quantities relevant to the mechanism reduction [24]. Further details about the mathematical formulation are provided in Sec. S1 of the Supplementary Material. The maximum error tolerance allowed during the reduction algorithm is 5% on the ion current density, integrated heat release, and maximum temperature produced by the flame. The resulting reduced mechanism, which is fully described in the file provided in the Supplementary Material, consists of 26 species, including two positive ions (HCO^+ and H_3O^+), one negative ion (O_2^-), and the electrons, which react through 134 reactions.

Two reactions of the detailed kinetic mechanism, namely

and

have been modified to improve the predictions of ion current density. Similarly to the modifications made in

3. Discussion and conclusions

Figure 1 shows a comparison of the ion current per unit area of the burner produced by the premixed one-dimensional flame. The numerical results obtained by Speelman *et al.* [10] and Belhi *et al.* [12] are reported in the figure for reference. The plots in the figure clearly show the large overprediction of the ion current for the non-optimized mechanism proposed by Speelman *et al.* [10]. On the other hand, the optimized mechanism of Speelman *et al.* [10] and the detailed mechanism of Belhi *et al.* [12] show accurate predictions of the saturation current in the whole range of applied voltages and particularly at positive polarities. The results of the “modified” mechanism are in good agreement with the experiments, whereby the modifications introduced on the reactions (R1) and (R2) significantly improve the predictions of the ion current produced by the flames at $\phi = 0.8$ and 1.0 for positive polarities. The only conditions where the “detailed” mechanism provides better results than the modified set of reactions is at negative polarities of lean flame, where the black diamond symbols are much closer to the experimental data than the black circles. The reasons for these discrepancies and the resulting potential improvements to the proposed mechanism will be the subject of future investigations.

The reduced mechanism proposed in this work provides predictions for the ion-current density, the maximum temperature, and the total heat release rate that are within a 2%, 0.14%, and 0.03% difference with respect to the modified mechanism. This result is particularly useful in view of performing accurate direct numerical simulations of flames impinged by electric fields. In fact, this reduced mechanism considers only a small fraction of the species and reactions contained in the other chemical mechanisms. Considering that the complexity of the computational methods utilized for the discretization of the transport equations that describe electric field flames often scale with the number of solved species squared, this new mechanism will guarantee a significant reduction in the computational cost without introducing any penalty in the accuracy of the calculations.

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Supplementary Material

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S1. Mathematical formulation

This section of the Supplementary Material provides a description of the conservation equations and associated boundary conditions utilized to obtain the presented results. The description includes details of the calculation of transport properties considered in the model.

S1.1. Conservation equations

The one-dimensional mass conservation equation considered in this work read as

$$\frac{d(\rho u)}{dx} = 0, \quad (\text{S1.1})$$

where x is the coordinate in the flame-normal direction, ρ is the mixture density, u is the flame normal component of the flow velocity.

The local mixture composition is obtained by integrating the species conservation equation

$$\frac{d}{dx} [\rho(u + V_i) Y_i] = \rho \dot{w}_i, \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, N_s, \quad (\text{S1.2})$$

where N_s is the species in the gas mixture, Y_i is the mass fraction of species i , and \dot{w}_i and V_i are the corresponding chemical production rate and diffusion velocity, respectively. In particular, the diffusion velocity V_i is calculated from the expression

$$V_i = -\frac{D_i}{X_i} \frac{dX_i}{dx} + \mu_i \mathcal{S}_i E + \sum_{j=1}^{N_s} \left[\frac{Y_j}{X_j} D_j \frac{dX_j}{dx} - \mu_j \mathcal{S}_j Y_j E \right], \quad (\text{S1.3})$$

where X_i , D_i , and μ_i are, respectively, the molar fraction, mass diffusivity and electric mobility of species i . Additionally, \mathcal{S}_i is the number of elementary charges of the i -th species. In particular, $\mathcal{S}_i = 0$ for neutral species, and $\mathcal{S}_i > 0$ and $\mathcal{S}_i < 0$ for positively and negatively charged species, respectively. Three terms contribute to the evaluation of V_i : the first one represents the molecular diffusion flux in the Curtiss-Hirschfelder approximation [1]; the second one corresponds to a velocity drift of charged species that is induced by the local electric field E [2]; and the last term is a corrector flux that preserves the total mass of the multicomponent mixture [3].

The energy conservation equation is solved in the temperature form, namely

$$c_p \frac{d(\rho u T)}{dx} = \frac{d}{dx} \left(\lambda \frac{dT}{dx} \right) - \rho \sum_{i=1}^{N_s} Y_i c_{p_i} V_i \frac{dT}{dx} - \rho \sum_{i=1}^{N_s} h_i \dot{w}_i + \rho N_A e \sum_{i=1}^{N_s} \frac{\mathcal{S}_i Y_i}{W_i} V_i E, \quad (\text{S1.4})$$

where $c_p = \sum_{i=1}^{N_s} Y_i c_{p_i}$ is the mean specific heat at constant pressure, with c_{p_i} indicating the corresponding temperature-dependent value for species i . Additionally, $h_i = h_{i,ref} + \int_{T_0}^T c_{p_i} dT$ is the partial specific enthalpy, $h_{i,ref}$ is the reference enthalpy of the species i at the temperature T_0 , W_i is the molecular weight of species i , N_A is the Avogadro number, e is the absolute value of the electron charge, and λ is a thermal conductivity of the mixture. The right-hand side of Eq. (S1.4) includes the molecular heat conduction, a heat flux due to inter-diffusion of species, the heat released by the chemical reactions, and the Ohmic dissipation due to electric current.

The local electric field E is computed from a local potential Φ as

$$\mathbf{E} = -\frac{d\Phi}{dx}, \quad (\text{S1.5})$$

where Φ is obtained from the solution to the Gauss equation

$$\frac{d^2\Phi}{dx^2} = -\frac{\rho_q}{\epsilon_0}, \quad (\text{S1.6})$$

with ϵ_0 as the dielectric permittivity of vacuum. $\rho_q = \sum_{i=1}^{N_s} \rho_{q,i}$ appearing on the right-hand side of Eq. (S1.6) is the sum of the individual charge densities

$$\rho_{q,i} = \rho N_A e \frac{\mathcal{S}_i Y_i}{W_i} \quad (\text{S1.7})$$

representing the amount of charge carried by species i per unit volume.

The described system of differential equations is closed using the equation of state for an ideal multi-component gas

$$P = \rho R^0 T / \bar{W}, \quad (\text{S1.8})$$

where $\bar{W} = (\sum_{i=1}^{N_s} Y_i / W_i)^{-1}$ is the mean molecular weight, R^0 is the universal gas constant, and P is the thermodynamic pressure, which is assumed uniform.

It is noteworthy that the Lorentz force associated with the ion-wind appears only in the momentum conservation equation in low-Mach number one-dimensional flows. This equation, which is not reported here for brevity, is not required during the solution of the flow but it can be utilized in a post-processing phase to compute the hydrodynamic pressure distribution [4].

S1.2. Transport coefficients

The individual binary diffusivities (D_{ij}) are evaluated from the kinetic theory as in Hirschfelder *et al.* [5]

$$D_{ij} = \frac{3}{16} \frac{\sqrt{2\pi N_A k_B^3 T^3 / W_{ij}}}{p\pi\sigma_{ij}^2 \Omega_{ij}^{(1,1)}}, \quad (\text{S1.9})$$

where k_B is the Boltzmann constant, $\sigma_{ij} = (\sigma_i + \sigma_j)/2$ is the reduced collision diameter computed using the Lennard-Jones collision diameters σ_i , and $W_{ij} = W_i W_j / (W_i + W_j)$ is the reduced molecular weight. Additionally, $\Omega_{ij}^{(1,1)}$ is collision integrals that are expressed as polynomials of the reduced temperature $T_{ij}^* = T k_B / \sqrt{\xi_i \xi_j}$, where ξ_i is the potential well-depth of species i . In this study, the Stockmayer potential [6] is employed to calculate the integral $\Omega_{ij}^{(1,1)}$ as function of the reduced temperature and reduced dipole moment for collision among neutral species. On the other hand, the (n,6,4)-potential is utilized to compute the interactions among charged and neutral species [7]. Collisions among charged particles have been neglected. Such collisions are expected to provide negligible contribution to the mixture average transport properties of the species because of the very small concentrations of charged species ($X_i \sim 10^{-8}$) observed in the conditions under exam.

The individual thermal conductivities are estimated as a function of the pure species viscosities and specific heats using the expression provided in Ref. [8]. The temperature dependence of the individual specific heats c_{p_i} are modeled using the NASA polynomials [9].

The mass diffusivities of each component of the mixture is then averaged using the approximate expression

$$D_i = (1 - Y_i) \left/ \sum_{j=1, j \neq i}^{N_s} \frac{X_j}{D_{ij}} \right. \quad (\text{S1.10})$$

proposed by Bird *et al.* [10], with D_{ij} given by Eq. (S1.9). The mixture averaging rule from Ref. [11] is followed to calculate the thermal conductivity λ of the mixture as function of the λ_i , namely

$$\lambda = \frac{1}{2} \left[\sum_{i=1}^{N_s} X_i \lambda_i + \left(\sum_{i=1}^{N_s} \frac{X_i}{\lambda_i} \right)^{-1} \right]. \quad (\text{S1.11})$$

The binary mobilities of the heavy ions, μ_{ij} are obtained from the Einstein relation [12]

$$\frac{D_{ij}}{\mu_{ij}} = \frac{k_B T}{e}, \quad (\text{S1.12})$$

Figure S1.1: Laminar flame speed predicted by the reduced mechanism (black line) and by the modified mechanism (black circles).

while the corresponding mixture-averaged value μ_i is computed using the expression [12]

$$\mu_i = \left(\sum_{j=1}^{N_s} \frac{X_j}{\mu_{ij}} \right)^{-1}. \quad (\text{S1.13})$$

In this formulation, the electron mobility μ_{e^-} is set to the constant value of $0.2 \text{ m}^2 / (\text{s V})$, which provides accurate estimation of the electric saturation voltage of the tested flames. Consistently with this choice, the electron mass diffusivity D_{e^-} is computed with the Einstein relation

$$D_{e^-} = \frac{k_B \mu_{e^-} T}{e}. \quad (\text{S1.14})$$

More accurate formulations for the electron mobility, that provide spatially varying distributions of μ_{e^-} as function of the local mixture composition and thermodynamic state, are available in the literature Bisetti and El Morsli [13]. However, it has been decided to defer the inclusions of these models to future studies to simplify the mixture description in view of including the proposed reduced mechanism in a multidimensional fluid dynamic solver.

S1.3. Boundary conditions

The described transport equations are discretized over a one-dimensional computational grid using a second-order finite difference scheme. The upstream boundary condition is an inflow which imposes the flux of the injected species, the temperature of the burner as well as the mass flow rate. Conversely, the downstream boundary condition is an outflow that extrapolates the conserved quantities.

The Eq. (S1.6) is closed using two Dirichlet boundary conditions that set the electric potential at the two boundaries of the computational domain. For the specific setup

Figure S1.2: Profiles of ion current density produced by the flame at $\phi = 0.6$ (a) and 1.4 (b). The black circles and the black solid line correspond to the prediction of the modified mechanism and reduced mechanism, respectively.

under exam, the electric potential at the upstream boundary is set to zero, whereas the value of Φ at the downstream boundary is equal to the applied voltage.

The boundary conditions for the ionized species are imposed depending on the direction of the species drift. If the electrically charged species is electrostatically attracted to the electrode, a zero normal-gradient condition is imposed on the corresponding mass fraction Y_i . Conversely, if electrostatic repulsion prevails, the mass fraction of the charged species is set to zero to prevent any unrealistic injection of ions released by the electrode.

S2. Prediction on neutral chemistry

The accuracy of the proposed mechanism in predicting the neutral chemistry of a methane/air flame is assessed in this section by comparing the laminar flame speed predicted by the reduced, detailed, and modified mechanisms. The considered setup consists in a freely propagating flame at ambient pressure, where the unburnt gas is at 298 K. It is noteworthy that this setup and these thermodynamic conditions are not included in the configurations utilized by the reduction algorithm.

Figure S1.1 shows the computed values of laminar flame speed. The data points computed using the detailed and modified mechanisms are coincident. This result demonstrates that the changes to the kinetic parameters of the reactions (R1) and (R2) do not introduce any significant modification to the neutral chemistry. The reduced mechanism provides predictions that are very similar to those of other two mechanisms. The only significant difference observed in the analyzed testcase is at $\phi = 1.4$. For this case, the laminar flame speed predicted by the reduced mechanism is about 10% lower than the reference value.

S3. Performance in richer and leaner conditions

The accuracy of the proposed mechanism is discussed in conditions that are outside the range of conditions utilized during the reduction algorithm. In particular, two electrified burner-stabilized flames at leaner ($\phi = 0.6$) and richer ($\phi = 1.4$) equivalence ratios have been computed with the modified and reduced mechanisms.

Figure S1.2 shows a comparison of the ion current density profiles computed with the two mechanisms. Very good agreement is observed overall. The saturation current is under-predicted by about 5% by the reduced mechanism. This results highlights potential improvements in the determination of the constraints utilized in the reduction algorithm. At the same time, this error, which is comparable with the differences between the state-of-the-art detailed mechanisms and the experimental data, is considered acceptable in view of the computational cost reduction guaranteed by the proposed reduced mechanism.

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